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Cloud for Data-Driven Policy Management

CLOUD FOR DATA-DRIVEN POLICY MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: This deliverable will include the specification of the tools used to model and design the policies as well as the design of the policy development toolkit, and the mechanisms required for the compilation of policies collections to perform cross-sector analysis and policy making. It will also architect the tools to identify groups for data-driven policies experimentation and adaptation.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
BDA	Big Data Analytics
DAA	Data Acquisition and Analytics
DPA	Data Processing Agreement
DSS	Decision Support System
EC	European Commission
GDPR	Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PDT	Policy Development Toolkit
PM	Policy Model
PME	Policy Model Editor
PP	Public Policy
SOA	Service Oriented Architecture
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
UX	User eXperience
UML	Unified Modelling Language

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Executive Summary

This document is an incremental update of deliverable D5.2 [1] and details the specification of the tools and technologies used to model Public Policies (PPs) as well as the design of the policy development toolkit (including the visualization framework), and the mechanisms required for compilation of policy collections to perform cross-sector analysis. The purpose of this series of deliverables is to keep track of the specifications throughout the project and update them as the project progresses.

This deliverable has been released in M20 (August 2021) of the project, and its main objective is to describe the approach to the policy modelling and validation that will support policy makers in the design, evaluation, optimization and adaptation of policies. The Policy Development Toolkit (PDT), along with the Policy Model Editor (PME), constitute the front-end of the PolicyCLOUD platform, which allows policy makers to create, update and validate policies. The PDT backend, which hides the complexity of storing the data models into persistent storage, implements the services that the front-end uses to display the content to the user and provide the necessary user experience.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This document is the second iteration of “Cross-Sector Policy Lifecycle Management: Design and Specifications”, and covers tasks T5.2, T5.3, T5.4 and T5.5. Its main purpose is to provide the updated approach to the policy modelling and evaluation that will be used in PolicyCLOUD to support policy makers in the creation, modelling, and evaluation of their Public Policies.

This report will be further refined during the last phase of the project’s duration. There will be an additional version of this document in month M32 (August 2022) that will finalise the deliverable and include any further advancements and contributions from other tasks.

1.2 Summary of changes

The main changes in this deliverable regard the addition of Sections 4 and 6. In addition, we enhanced/revised/updated the rest of the document (including figures) in order to reflect the current work done in M20 (August 2021).

1.3 Structure of the Document

The rest of the document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 introduces the definition of Public Policies, including state-of-the-art concepts on PPs development that cover why, what, and how they are developed and who is actively or passively affected by the policies.
- Section 3 presents the conceptual methodologies proposed for policy modelling, based mainly on the concepts of ontology and semantic reasoning technologies. It also proposes an updated approach on policy modelling and their evaluation based on the concept of KPIs.
- Section 4 describes the mechanisms required for compilation of policy collections / clusters to perform cross-sector analysis.
- Section 5 introduces the architecture of the PDT and describes the various User Interfaces (UIs) components, including the Data Visualization Framework.
- Section 6 details the legal and ethical considerations and requirements.
- Finally, Section 7 provides the conclusion of the document.

2 Public Policies

A *public policy* (PP) is a plan, course of action, or set of regulations adopted by a policy maker to influence and determine decisions or procedures that affect a group of public and private actors in order to achieve a desired outcome. The policy maker gathers information through public consultation and scientific research to extract the necessary knowledge base and creates a policy, or a set of policies, which serve to define and promote a preferred course of action (or inaction). This, in turn, will allow targets and points of reference to be established for the short and medium term. In PolicyCLOUD, we include, within the concept of “policy makers”, government bureaucrats and technocrats from various sectors (e.g., healthcare, education, security, environment, etc.) and public sector staff who implement and evaluate programs.

A PP is carried out following a defined process, considering the context and characteristics of the geographic area (city, region, country) where it must be implemented, with the purpose of driving the PP’s content. PPs will pertain to some actors, which must be considered during their design. When a PP is developed, a proper evaluation process shall be defined to assess whether the actions or inactions considered are fulfilling the defined goals. The evaluation process includes the definition and measurement of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to assess if the proposed goals are reached (and to what extent), and to evaluate if the correct parameters were selected to meet this goal. KPIs are generally presented to a group of key actors that are interested in the results of the PPs, in order to decide whether to continue with the same policies, apply corrective measures, or to partially or completely redefine the content of the PPs. This schema is illustrated in Figure 1, as proposed by Gagnon and Labonté [2].

FIGURE 1 – POLICY ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK

2.1 Actors

Actors are defined as individuals, groups, or organizations that are relevant decision-makers and/or parties interested in monitoring the effect and evolution of a PP that has been created or modified.

In PolicyCLOUD, we group actors in two categories, depending on their ability to take decisions when formulating the content of a PP:

- **formal actors** are defined as actors who belong to the public authorities at any level (local, regional, national, international) and are responsible for the definition of the PPs and, thus, have formal political power or are direct policy makers;
- **informal actors** are defined as actors who do not have any political power and, thus, are outside of the decision-making process, but can still have a scientific or political influence on the final decisions, such as the civil society, NGOs, etc.

The PolicyCLOUD project will be mainly focused on formal actors, since the goal of the project is to serve as a Decision Support System (DSS) for policy making. This does not mean, however, that policy making using the PolicyCLOUD system will be performed without considering the input from other relevant stakeholders. Indeed, informal actors could be considered as key entities or groups for the purpose of evaluating the KPIs. Hence, PolicyCLOUD will consider which actors should be informed on the results of the KPIs related to the PP developed.

2.2 Context

The context of a PP defines why the PP is needed and refers to those cultural, structural, situational and/or external factors relevant to the PP and which may have a relevant effect on a given society.

- **Cultural factors** refer to the existence of formal/informal hierarchies, different languages or ethnic minorities that may affect the equity of a PP, gender role, and the importance of religious factors, among others.
- **Structural factors** are stable elements of the society, such as the political system, the level of participation of the civil society in the discussion and decision process, the economic system, etc.
- **Situational factors** are temporary conditions, such as epidemics, natural disasters, or austerity measures in times of economic crisis, that may also have an influence on PPs and/or affect the monitoring of PPs in temporary situations.
- **Other factors** refer to conditions of inter-dependence between states, cooperation among organizations/states or international laws and norms that may affect PPs.

The full context of PPs is not directly integrated in the policy modelling tasks of PolicyCLOUD, since this cannot be modelled directly. However, the PolicyCLOUD system will encourage policy makers to consider all the relevant contextual factors before developing any PP.

2.3 Content

The content refers to the main subject-matter of the PP, and to which questions are considered in the design of the PP. The content of a PP defines specific issues, problems and/or challenges and is linked directly to the domain it applies (e.g., security – uc#1, agri-food – uc#2, mobility and transport – uc#3, and employment – uc#4). Some examples for each domain are provided below:

Security:

- How to improve access to public spaces
- How to increase efficient use of resources (e.g., number of police officers in the territory)
- How to promote a better inclusion of different groups in the society (e.g., dedicated programmes and activities targeting specific groups, such as immigrants or minorities)

Agri-food:

- What trends exist in the wine sector
- How to increase sales in an increasingly competitive market
- How to increment the market of the D.O. Aragon product show
- How to increase efficient use of resources for marketing activities

Mobility and transport:

- How to efficiently allocate resources
- How to proactively target areas for preventive measures
- How to improve transport and parking utilisation and customer experience
- How to identify trends and problem concentration areas

Employment

- How different groups of population are affected by unemployment
- How to predict future trends and potential problems

The content of a PP cannot be separated from the dimension of the process (how the PP is carried out), the actors (who define the PP and need to be informed on its evolution), the context (where the PP will be implemented and what specificities it should have), the stakeholders (who are affected by the PP), and the evaluation (what impact is the PP having, as measured by KPIs that should have been defined previously).

The purpose of the PolicyCLOUD project is to support policy makers in developing the content of the PP as an evidence-based outcome of the PolicyCLOUD system.

2.4 Process

The process defines how the PP was brought forward and implemented. The process of policy making can be seen as a methodology or approach that is defined by seven phases, which extends the policy analysis cycles provided by Patton and Sawicki 1993 [3] (see Figure 2):

FIGURE 2 – POLICY ANALYSIS PROCESS

In the first phase, the policy maker **defines and details the given problem** by characterizing the social context in which the problem is embedded and identifying the independent variables that affect policy outcomes. It is the role of the policy maker to understand the positions and influence of various stakeholders and to choose the definition that the problem owner/decision maker has control on. Clarification of the problem takes place with consultation, brainstorming, narratives, and scientific research.

In the second phase, the policy maker **identifies the evaluation criteria** that determine when the problem is solved or a goal is accomplished. She/he will select those criteria that are central to the problem and most relevant to the decision makers in the implementation process [3].

Once the policy maker knows the values, objectives, and goals of the stakeholders and the evaluation criteria for validating the policies, she/he can generate a list of possible policies. This list is usually long since there are many variations and combinations. Benchmarking and past experience are common approaches for **identifying policy alternatives** to be implemented [4] [3].

Among policy alternatives, the most appropriate options are selected using the already defined evaluation criteria, leading thus to the **formulation of the policy**. The different alternatives are assessed based on the potential impact and their chain of causation. Since not every policy can be tested with the same method, various methods (e.g., cost-benefit analysis, programming, institutional analysis, and quantitative analysis) to evaluate different policies can be used.

The next phase is **policy implementation**. This is the most important phase, since it is aimed at setting up the public authority's planned actions in the way intended by the PP, to achieve the expected impact and results. In most instances, the policy maker develops implementation guidelines and procedures rather than being directly involved in the implementation of the selected PP.

The final phase is the **monitoring and evaluation** of the implemented PP. This requires the involvement of both formal and informal actors. In particular, this phase is about monitoring the use of inputs and the achievement of outputs, as well as evaluating the direct effects and medium-/long-term impacts of the PP, to provide evidence on whether the PP is achieving its objectives. It is important for the policy maker to know whether a failed PP did not achieve the intended results because it was not implemented as designed, or because the PP's underlying theory was incorrect [3].

Although in common daily practice these stages lack clear separation, the PolicyCLOUD system is mainly devoted to directly helping the policy maker in the policy creation and decision-making stages, as well as, indirectly, in the policy implementation and policy evaluation stages.

2.5 Impact

Proper information management and monitoring is of utmost importance to enhance decision-making and to monitor and track evolution of a PP that have been implemented. A useful tool in this regard is the definition and measurement of the KPIs, as described in the above paragraphs. KPIs are metrics that are determined through scientific evidence or through the consensus of experts (when evidence is unavailable) to provide feedback to key actors about the results being achieved and to use this information to improve PPs.

Information is a key resource for developing specific KPIs that enable the measurement of each goal. KPIs are also a tool that needs to be reported for accountability reasons to those agents who may be responsible or who must take informed decisions on existing PPs and their possible updates. In addition, to develop good indicators, a set of common criteria could be used to aid the experts and final users in reaching a consensus on which indicators should be considered. To this end, the KPIs should be valid, specific, measurable, reliable, evidence-based, achievable, feasible, relevant, time-bounded, i.e., reported at regular intervals.

The benefits of using KPIs are several, including mainly the ability to assess the outcomes of PPs, the ability to compare equal parameters among different organizations following a benchmarking process of sharing improvements, the promotion of accountability to relevant actors, the promotion of

transparency (e.g., by allowing a public reporting of results), and the identification of areas for further research.

An example of a KPI from an existing PP from use case 3 is provided below.

Business KPIs	Success indicators
Increased brand awareness and reputation in social media	Number of posts, comments, retweets
Identified the most interesting concepts and trends in wine markets	Number of new terms identified Number of influencers identified
Brand analysis: quality vs price vs taste	
Prediction analysis: quality of the next crop	

TABLE 1 – DEFINITION OF THE KPIS FOR THE USE CASE OF ARAGON

3 Policy Modelling and Configuration

3.1 Modelling Methodologies

3.1.1 Ontologies

Policy modelling and decision-making knowledge is often represented as a set of basic definitions such as alternatives, criteria, decision matrices, and decisions themselves. However, this domain is much richer, and many other related notions are useful to make right decisions: preferences, weights, thresholds, and so on. This knowledge must be formalized within a model. In addition, the practical needs for policy making as well as the research dealing with decision-making, are increasingly growing as, for instance, in Information System engineering.

This kind of modelling is justified by the necessity to show different semantic links existing between policy making concepts. We have elaborated the ontology to represent concepts of the policy making domain, as well as their properties and relations.

The starting point for analysing the ontology (see Figure 3) is the situation. The situation is an abstract concept that puts together the main elements and describes a set of specific conditions dealing with a given object. The object is an artifact which is the subject of decision-making.

Activity	Expense	Sub partial Item
Budget	Expenses Classifier	Subprogram
Budget Analytic	Expense Object	Program Executer Unit (UEP)
Budget Approved	Finality Function	Programmatic Category
Budget Project Draft	Financial Administration	Project
Budget Synthetic	Financing Source	Public Funds Administrative Service (SAFOP)
Budget States	Geographic Locate	Rector Organism
Budgetary Classifier	Institutional	Resource
Budgetary Fiscal Year	Institutional	Resources Estimation
Budgetary Policy	Jurisdiction	Year Financial Administrative Service (SAF)
Budgetary Top	Program	
Executor Organism	Program	

TABLE 2 – KEY TERMS

3.1.1 Semantic reasoning and querying

Semantic queries allow for queries and analytics of an associative and contextual nature. Semantic queries enable the retrieval of both explicitly and implicitly derived information based on syntactic, semantic, and structural information contained in a policy data store. They are designed to deliver precise results (possibly the distinctive selection of one single piece of information) or to answer fuzzier and wide-open questions through pattern matching and digital reasoning.

Semantic queries work on named graphs, linked data, or triples. This enables the query to process the actual relationships between information and infer answers from the network of data. From a technical point of view, semantic queries are precise relational-type operations much like a database query. They work on structured data and therefore have the possibility to utilize comprehensive features like operators (e.g., >, < and =), namespaces, pattern matching, sub-classing, transitive relations, semantic rules, and contextual full text search.

The system will be able to automatically integrate data from different sources by replacing the context-dependent keys in the JSON output with URLs pointing to semantic vocabularies, that will be used to represent and link the data.

3.2 Policy Modelling

3.2.1 Data model

A *policy model (PM)* is an instantiation of the data model. At the second development phase of the project, the data model that we relied on in the first phase has been updated to include the entity of a *domain* that is related with various already defined entities, and to update the definition of the *data model* and *Analytical Tool* that is being currently used, after integration of the *Policy Model Editor (PME)* with the *Data Analytics and Acquisition (DAA)* layer implemented under the scope of WP4 activities. The current definition of the PM can be depicted in the following class diagram.

FIGURE 4 – POLICY MODEL CLASS DIAGRAM

From the class diagram, it can be concluded that there are several *entities* that are involved in a PM, and each one of those can be reused by other models. The central entity is the *policy* which holds all information regarding the specific model. This might be assigned to a specific policy maker, thus making this instance private to her/him, or might be public, thus being a model for the creation of new policies. This also allows the policy maker to search and explore her/his own policies. Each policy is associated

with a list of available *KPIs*, which defines the qualitative and quantitative indicators of the policy. KPIs are related with specific goals per stakeholder. It is important to highlight that our design enables the re-usability of KPIs, such that a well-defined KPI can be also used by other policies. As a result, there is a many-to-many relationship between the *policies* and the *KPIs* that allows for this to happen.

Moreover, each KPI is validated by a list of analytical tools that performs the processing and produces the results. The analytical tools might be of different type (e.g., sentiment analysis, opinion mining, risk assessment, etc.) and can be related with one or many different data sources. Therefore, an analytical tool is not implemented and locked-in for a specific data source, but can be a general-purpose tool applied to several data models.

The data model has been further extended in this second phase of the project by including the *domain* entity. The latter is related with various other entities, such as the *policy*, *kpi*, *actor* and *stakeholder*. This allows the PME to retrieve existing *policies*, *kpis* etc. according to the domain they are associated with. To have a formal way for all these entities to be filtered and returned to the PME, we put this information in a separate entity that holds a list of supported domains.

A main differentiator between the current design and the one we relied on in the first phase of the project, is that the information related with the entity *analytical tool* is not stored to the persistent storage that the PME uses. Instead, this information is dynamically retrieved by the DAA layer. The analytic provider registers her/his tool to the DAA by using the mechanisms developed under WP4, and the DAA layer publishes programmatically this type of information. The latter includes the endpoint to be invoked in order to trigger the execution of the analytical processing, the input parameters that requires etc. This information is collected by the PDT via the invocation of a REST interface and is represented by the *AnalyticalToolConfiguration* entity of the data model. Moreover, as each of the tools might be configured differently according to its purpose (i.e., it might be able to return results in different formats to be visualized by different graphs), the *AnalyticalTool* entity contains the specific information on how the tool will be instantiated to be used by the *KPI* that is related with.

Finally, when an analytical tool is invoked, this submits a *job* for execution. Since the processing of a dataset can be a long-running process, the invocation of tools is asynchronous. Therefore, a new *job* is created, and when the analysis is concluded, the result of the latter can be stored in that job.

To summarize, this data model for policies allows for great flexibility, as it avoids duplicating entities and instead, it allows for the re-usability and the addition of new elements that can be offered in the ecosystem. A policy maker can have a list of *policies*, or explore the *PMs*, validate the existing KPIs that might be applied in different domains, and investigate why some of them can be beneficial across domain sectors, and why others are more related to specific ones. The proposed solution also allows for the provision of additional analytical tools that can be developed in the future and can be easily plugged in to the platform and made available to any existing PM. Their retrieval is being done dynamically by requesting them from the underlying DAA layer. That way, the provider of the data analytics has to register the tool once, and this can be then discovered by the upper layers, which model this information accordingly.

This gives an absolute freedom for the policy maker to validate different aspects and KPIs using a variety of different tools. It should be highlighted at this point that the process of defining the data model of the *policies* is done through an agile approach, and we might need to further extend the proposed schema in the last version of this deliverable, once additional feedback from the policy makers and domain experts of our four use cases is received.

3.2.2 Policy Model Editor

The Policy Model Editor (PME) is the component that lie into the PolicyCLOUD front-end. The purpose is to create new policies and edit existing ones following the evaluation process.

As described in Section 5.1 the PME helps the user to create PPs by applying relevant KPIs that are stored into the PDT backend or compose new KPIs by defining Actors and Stakeholders to the PM, selecting the data source and the analytical tools that will process the data, and finally setting the parameter values that the analytical tools require to provide the result, and save the PM to the datastore.

Hence, we have developed and deployed a middleware which can be used as the adapter pattern, to retrieve data from the policies datastore. The middleware is a modelling tool based on .NET Core that lies between the datastore (after the DAA layer) and the data visualization.

Essentially functioning as a hidden translation layer, the middleware enables communication and data management by users and allow them to perform requests by completing a simplified wizard (assistant).

4 Policy Collections and Cross-Sector Analysis

The main goal of the policy collections sub-component is to enable the development of collection / clusters of policies that will be used to retrieve relevant information for cross-sector analysis and therefore to compute the associated KPIs within the policy evaluation component.

Identification of the proper collection / cluster of policies is based on a set of inclusion and exclusion criteria, which are used to calculate the KPI used to evaluate the policies through the execution of the analytical models, regardless of their nature, i.e., single, aggregated, composite or indexes. These inclusion and exclusion criteria include information that is utilized to identify the collection / cluster of policies under study and also information regarding the variables that have been selected for each. Examples of such criteria consider location perspective (e.g., district, city, region, country), demographics aspects (e.g., age groups), or other dimensions (e.g., gender, education).

UC1 - Maggioli	UC2 - Sarga	UC3 - Sofia	UC4 - London
Age group	Age group	Location	Age group
Location	Gender	Sub-domain	Gender
Sub-domain	Education	Sector	Education
	Location		Location

The identification of the collection / cluster of policies is performed by means of a list of parameters with their minimum and maximum thresholds that are transformed into specific queries to retrieve the data from the data store. For example, if a dataset from adult population is needed to compute a KPI, a parameter to be included in the population segmentation component (see Section 5.1.1) may include “age” as a variable to be taken into account, along with a “minimum” attribute with a value of “18” and a “maximum” attribute with a value of “60”. Subsequently, this parameter can be transformed into a filter condition of a query that will be applied to retrieve the set of data with the corresponding variables that have to be used for computing such a KPI and thus evaluating the defined policy.

Hence, there is a need to update the common policy model schema that will provide all necessary information for the definition of the parameters used in the filter conditions for the collection / cluster of policies identification, as explained in the previous paragraphs. This information will be developed by using JSON objects that encapsulate all the needed attributes and sub-elements to represent the parameters, and its structure.

5 Policy Development Toolkit

The present section describes the functionalities of the Policy Development Toolkit (PDT). As a web application, the PDT consists of the front-end that allows policy makers to evaluate Policy Models (PMs), and the backend that hides the complexity of storing the data models into persistent storage and implements the services that the front-end uses to display the content to the user and provide the necessary user experience (UX). The PDT will intentionally hide the complexity of the system dataflow to provide the user with a Decision Support System (DSS) towards evidence-based Public Policies (PPs).

5.1 Architecture

The general interconnection of the PDT with the other PolicyCLOUD components is illustrated in Figure 5. The PDT enables the processing of data through the exploitation of collective knowledge that emerges from multiple information sources. The platform explores mechanisms that can be clustered across two main areas: analytics on heterogenous data at population and individual level and predefined PMs exploiting community knowledge across different ecosystems. The PDT may be considered as the point of integration and interaction of the platform with the policy makers. Through the PDT, the policy makers through the use of KPIs are able to query the platform data and exploit the analytics tools, in order to create and evaluate PPs.

5.1.1 PDT Design

FIGURE 5 – PDT COMMUNICATION COMPONENTS

Figure 5 shows the two components with which the PDT communicates directly: Backend/Datastore and Analytics Tools from the DAA Layer. Both components expose API Interfaces so that the User Interface (UI) receives the data from the Datastore and sends to the Analytics for processing the parameters that the policy maker has selected through the PME for the respective KPI.

In the proposed architecture [5] each component is decoupled from the others. This modular structure allows versatility and extensibility, by means of analytics tools providers, analytics frameworks, cloud providers and deployment patterns, while keeping a stable level of trustworthiness. For example, the DAA layer's modularity permits the easy addition of various categories of analytics tools (such as simulation, social network analysis, semantic and linked data etc.), which are earmarked for policy-making purposes. This, in consequence, supports the policy maker in the creation of PMs that are based on the composition of related KPIs. The modular UI intentionally hides the big complexity of the platform's inner processes from users, as each component is decoupled and focused on their own properties and functions (in an object-oriented perspective). So, a PM is composed and supported by related KPIs, which, in turn, are composed of related Analytics Tools that provide their own visualization graphs. A Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) pattern is followed by requiring the components to adhere to a common communication protocol (such as the Analytics Tools registration payload), and by exposing consistent RESTful APIs. This allows different Analytics Tools providers and big data technologies to co-exist and collaborate to create a policy related ecosystem. This modular structure also supports scalability. Each module, depending on the load it receives on a case-by-case basis, can resort to load balancing solutions.

Regarding the modular design of the DAA layer, this allows each Analytics Tool developer to employ different Big Data Analytics (BDAs) frameworks, using various deployment configuration mechanisms. This decoupled and distributed architecture provides fertile ground for the growth of an Analytics Tools Store, where Data Experts may develop specialized Analytics Tools and register them in the PolicyCLOUD platform, via its corresponding DAA layer, which can subsequently be invoked by the PDT using a common data model that the tools must follow (via a common protocol). In consequence, Analytics Tools can operate and provide their services under different financial procedures, including commercialized options. This way, new PMs can be formulated, based on KPIs that utilize Analytics Tools.

In detail, the arrows in Figure 5 shows the content of the communication on each side. The policy maker, via the PDT, is able to retrieve a list of existing policies, and view the structure and content of a PM. The display of policies via the PDT is based on the aforementioned PM that is being fed by the data that are stored in the Datastore and are retrieved by the backend services in JSON format.

The User also has access to the registered analytics tools, via the KPIs that are linked with a selected PM. Once an Analytics Tool has been selected for the evaluation of a KPI, the parameter's values are sent to the analytics to start the execution of KPI evaluation. This is being taking care by the DAA layer, highlighting our modular approach where each component is only focusing on its own functionality. The PDT provides the user interface that facilitates the policy maker to perform the evaluation, and requests the execution of analytics by communicating with the DAA layer that is responsible for these activities. The User is notified about the submission process, the status of a submitted job, and has the ability to receive and view the results of the Analytics, as the results are communicated to the backend by the DAA layer that monitors the execution of the analysis.

The blue level in Figure 5 represents the process of semantic reasoning and querying. Based on the process set out in Section 3.1, the semantic processing of emerging policies for lifecycle policy modeling

intervenes. The metadata provided by this level, together with reasoning, enables the validation of the policy structure in terms of their proper construction. They also help policy makers to choose KPIs, avoid dysfunctional policies, and provide cross-sectional policy optimization information.

The greyed arrows in Figure 5 depict the communication of the DAA layer with the Backend/Datastore which include calls for the invocation of the Analytics Tool, notifications about the status of submitted jobs and their results, as well as queries for data retrieval from the Datastore in order to perform the analytics calculations and produce results. PDT does not access directly the datasets contained in the Datastore but receives the processed / aggregated data produced by the Analytics Tools in the form of a single, properly structured JSON file per each KPI evaluation submission. The contents of the JSON file are being forwarded internally to the visualization component for the creation of the proper graph.

The following is a list of basic functions that the PDT will provide to the policy makers:

- User Login
- User Profile
- Policy Model Viewer (implementation pending)
- Policy Evaluations / Analytics
- Transactions History (This component offers a consistent way of displaying all the Analytics Results that the user has submitted to Analytical Tools along with the selected parameter values) (implementation pending)
- Getting Help

An updated Storyboard suggestion follows:

5.1.1.1 STORYBOARD

INTRODUCTION

After login, the initial page will initiate the PM evaluation process.

We call this component/module 'policy development toolkit' by convention, although it helps policy makers to create a real-world policy for example, a political targeting as:

"Do something (like lower the taxes for sugar free products) for population on high risk regarding obesity".

For our system, a corresponding policy-query (and making/evaluation via controls/menus) could be:

"Identify high risk population regarding obesity" (simplified by what policy maker quantitatively evaluates via wizard)".

The results may show age group 40-50 male, so the targeting products that are consumed from that group will help the policy maker to create the 'real world' policy.

A mockup is shown in Figure 6.

FIGURE 6 – MOCKUP: INITIAL PAGE AFTER LOGIN

The policy evaluation steps via the PDT are depicted in the following figure:

FIGURE 7 – POLICY EVALUATION STEPS VIA PDT

The PDT guides the user via a step wizard (policy wizard) to follow the hierarchical structure of the policy model. The user submits a job request for the execution of a specific analytics tool for the evaluation of selected KPI. The final step is the retrieval of the Analytics results, which contain the quantitative evaluations and are displayed via the internal visualization component.

POLICY WIZARD

FIGURE 8 – POLICY BUILDER: WIZARD FOR THE END USERS (IMPLEMENTATION MOCKUP)

The user loads a PM from the model’s repository. Each model is associated with some goals/objectives and could include some predefined queries for population segmentation and a list of KPIs.

At page initialization, the KPIs are fetched dynamically from the datastore via the backend exposed API (instead of being hard coded options in the code). This way, KPIs are referring to different entities that can be reused and updated by just adding them in the PDT backend.

Some options can be static; for example, the age, gender, and timeline.

For the rest of controls, appropriate APIs with the available options are offered for policy makers (see below), at the PME design stage.

FIGURE 9 – POPULATION SEGMENTATION (IMPLEMENTATION MOCKUP)

FIGURE 10 – TIMEFRAME SELECTION OPTION

At initialization of the page, the controls that are dynamically populated (as mentioned above) are populated with 'options' from component/modules such as, e.g., analytics.

The front-end retrieves the corresponding analytical tools that are related with a specific policy, along with their meta-information, such as the parameters that are expecting, their types, allowed values etc. This information is retrieved by invoking web methods exposed by the backend as REST services. The response of such a request is a JSON object with this information, and which allows the front end to dynamically and accordingly draw the content of the page.

In order to do so, we have modeled the input parameters that each of the analytical tools will expect. This provides a generic and common way for all tools to describe these parameters so that the front-end of the PDT can invoke all registered tools in a common manner via well-established protocols. This will also allow the frontend of the PDT to become extensible, so as to allow for future tools to be plugged-in and avoid being locked-in to specific implementations. The model definition of the parameters can be depicted in Figure 11:

FIGURE 11 – CLASS DIAGRAM OF THE PARAMETERS

An *AParameter* describes an available parameter required by the analytical tool. It is of a specific type, might contain a list of different constraints, and has a specific evaluation type. When this parameter also has a concrete value, assigned during the runtime, then this value can be of different types, according to the *EvaluationType*.

The *EvaluationType* can be one of the following: EQUAL, LESS, LESS_OR_EQUAL, GREATER, GREATER_OR_EQUAL, IS, NOT, RANGE, IN

The *ValueConstraintType* can be one of the following: DEFAULT, VALUESALLOWED, MIN, MAX, STEP.

The *ParameterValueType* can be one of the following: BOOLEAN, INTEGER, FLOAT, STRING.

For instance, in the aforementioned example, the KPI named *life expectancy* is related with a parameter of type *date*, which accepts a range of values. Therefore, the front-end will retrieve this information via the corresponding REST service to dynamically draw two fields to fill the *from* and *to* values of the *range* and will provide 2 *calendar* objects for the user to insert his/her input during the policy model design (PME). All the selected parameter values are shown in PDT after the user has created the policy model, and the related JSON file has been created into the PDT Backend. To summarize, the backend provides all this information that describes the analytical tools and the front-end provides a wizard to facilitate the start of an analysis. In each of the steps of this wizard, the front-end asks the backend for the corresponding meta-information, and dynamically adjusts to improve the overall UX of the user.

FIGURE 12 – INIZIALIZATION OF UI CONTROLS FROM THE DATASTORE POLICY MODEL

SUMMARIZE AND SUBMIT

After the initialization of the PDT according to the selected policy and the adjustment of the UI with respect to the meta-information provided by each analytical tool upon its registration, the policy maker is now able to experiment by providing her options to the toolkit and submit a request for execution of the analytical tool(s).

FIGURE 13 – RESULTS FROM ANALYTICS FETCHED FROM BACKEND AND VISUALISED IN PDT

It should be noted that the PDT does not make policies, but rather assists policy maker in policy development, offering a single and integrated entry point (one stop shop approach) to the PolicyCLOUD analytics and Visualization tools.

USER (POLICY MAKER) HISTORY OF POLICIES

The end user will be able to see any of her previously created policy models and their structure (e.g., related KPIs and Analytics Tools).

5.1.2 Data Visualisation Framework

The Data Visualization Framework, a sub-component of the PDT, aims to help policy makers in the policy creating process, as well as in its subsequent follow-up. This help comes in the form of different charts, graphs, tables, and any other kind of visualization defined, enabling policy makers to check in a glance the results of selected data analytics queries outcomes.

In a first approach each pilot has defined the best set of visualizations to fulfill their needs. These first defined visualizations can be changed after discussions and further analysis of available data.

At this point of the project, the balance between the available data and the charts initially proposed by the UCs owners is closer. In the case of UC1 “Participatory policies against radicalization”, Scenario A: Radicalization incidents, for example, the proposed Heat Map turned out to be also feasible, considering the available data. After an initial data review by WP4, it was verified that the available data allows the necessary information to be sent to paint the graph. From there, a common format for sending this information was agreed, in order to be received by the Visualization Component and allow it to paint the Heat Map. The PDT Backend sends the information in JSON format to the Visualization component, after taking it from the DAA layer. In the figure below we can see one example of the JSON received by the Visualization Component from the PDT Backend, when the chart to paint is the Heat Map:

```
{
  "id":2,
  "data":{
    "\num_events\":4,
    "\location\":{\type\:"Point",\coordinates\:[-100.5408, 42.642]},
    "\location2\":{\region\":1,\region_txt\:"North America"},
    "\startDate\":341513723145,
    "\endDate\":972662123145,
    "\events\":[
      {\eventid\": 201611250026,
        \year\": 2016,
        \latitude\": 47.154901,
        \longitude\": -122.368098,
        \summary\": "11/25/2016: Assailants set fire to Our Savior Lutheran Church in Tacoma, Washington, United States. There were no reported casualties in the attack. No group claimed responsibility for the incident.\",...}]}],
    "\typeOfCharts\": "HEATMAP_POI"
  }
}
```

FIGURE 14 – EXAMPLE OF A JSON FOR A HEAT MAP CHART

Once the Visualization Component receives the json in the agreed format, it can then paint the map:

FIGURE 15 – EXAMPLE OF A HEAT MAP CHART

Following the same procedure, another scenario that has also been defined was scenario B of the UC2: Intelligent policies for the development of agri-food industry, where the first charts were defined to be a Gauge and a Lineal:

FIGURE 16 – EXAMPLE OF A GAUGE CHART

Keywords: vines, vineyard, wine barrel, oenologist

FIGURE 17 – EXAMPLE OF A LINEAR CHART

Both charts are very useful in the sentiment analysis process, since they are capable of transmitting a large amount of information quickly and efficiently.

Other types of visualizations are also being described by UCs owners as very useful for each of their scenarios, but at the moment, although most of them are validated by the Visualization Component and a first approach of a json format is defined, they are still pending of a validation by the WP4, to confirm its viability taking into account the data available. In this case we have attractive types of visualizations like "Maps", that are a very illustrative and visual way to detect differences between regions and can be used into the Data Visualization Framework to present analytics results to the stakeholders. The type of map to be used is defined by the granularity of the data collected. Technologically a map that displays data at country, city or neighborhood level can be plotted, but this can only be done when the data source has enough information to do it.

FIGURE 18 – EXAMPLE OF A MAP VISUALIZATION

In line with above mentioned, other types of visualizations, like line, pie, bar, gauges or radar charts, can also provide a lot of information and could be very helpful, when the data source used is social network based, for example.

A bar chart is used to express, given a set of values, the accumulate quantity for each value. In the example below, it is used to show the quantity of each sentiment found from Facebook, for example:

FIGURE 19 – EXAMPLE OF CHARTS USED FOR SOCIAL MEDIA ANALYSIS VISUALIZATIONS: BAR CHART

Another example of a chart that could be fed by any social network data source are tag clouds (also known as word clouds), used to check the frequency of texts, using different sizes (bigger with higher frequency) and colors:

FIGURE 20 – EXAMPLE OF CHARTS USED FOR SOCIAL MEDIA ANALYSIS VISUALISATION: TAG CHART

Also, a radar chart could be useful, depending on the analyzed data. In the example below is shown an example with quality vs price vs integrity vs innovation vs speed vs consistency vs accuracy:

FIGURE 21 – EXAMPLE OF CHARTS USED FOR SOCIAL MEDIA ANALYSIS VISUALISATION: RADAR CHART

As can be seen, there are a lot of useful and functional charts that can be used in order to simplify and quickly show a big amount of information, that can come from any kind of data sources. The decision of which to use depends on the value they can provide to end users, taking into consideration their use cases, and the available data sources.

It is important to highlight that each of these charts will require result data to be provided in a predefined format that the chart supports. Therefore, the analytical tools, after data processing and the generation of the result, they need to provide the latter under the corresponding format in order for the charts to be compatible and in a position to visualize the graph. For that to happen, each tool announces upon registration the type of visualization that its results are compatible with and store the results,

respectively. Then, the PDT will be capable to retrieve the results stored in the data repository, check the type of chart that these results are related to, and initialize the graph with the data in the agreed format. At this point of the project, the initial list of charts that need to be supported at this phase, along with the capabilities of each of the available analytical tools, has been identified. This process has not been finished yet, and therefore, the definition of the data format that each chart needs to be compatible with, is still in progress and will be reported in the next version of this deliverable.

5.2 Baseline technologies and tools

The PDT is based on a Service Oriented Architecture and consists of the front-end part along with its backend, both aiming to facilitate and ease the interaction of the user with all the analytics components and the Datastore. The front end will be built as a Single Page Application developed using the Angular framework [6]. Angular is “a JavaScript-based open-source front-end web framework mainly maintained by Google and by a community of individuals and corporations to address many of the challenges encountered in developing single-page applications.” The open-sourced full-fledged Angular framework offers multiplatform support without particular hardware or other software requirements. It is based on Typescript programming language and JavaScript (as output) which is compatible with all browsers and mobile devices. For UI components and controls we will use the latest Angular Material library [7].

The Data Visualization Framework will also be developed with Angular Framework. Using a framework helps to achieve more functionalities in less time, as it provides reusable components, and makes developers work more efficient and easier.

With Angular framework, a lot of chart libraries can be used. One of these options could be, for example, amcharts library [8] that provides all possible charts mentioned in 4.1.2, among others. Any other chart library that can be used with Angular can be selected, and the final decision about it will be taken after the final set of charts is selected by end users to better fit their use cases.

Finally, the backend implementation of the PDT will be based on the Java release 8 [9], which can be easily installed and run in different environments. Additionally, according to the Service Oriented Architecture paradigm, it will implement and expose various REST APIs that will be used by the other components of the PDT. The REST web services will follow the JAX-RS specification, as described in the corresponding JSR-331 [10], JSR-339 [11] and JSR-370 [12] Java specification requests. The library that the backend will rely on for the implementation of these specifications will be Jersey [13]. The deployment of the backend will be using an embedded Java servlet container, to avoid the need to maintain an entire application server. The whole backend will be packaged in a single Java Archive (Jar) to ease the overall deployment. For the data repository of the PDT, we will rely on the LXS relational datastore that is the main pillar of the data management component of PolicyCLOUD.

6 Legal and Ethical Constraints

6.1 Constraints related to User Data

The information collected and stored in the PDT backend can essentially be divided into two categories:

- **Policy Data**, meaning the data which is collected from identified data sources and further processed by the Analytics Tools in the PDT backend, to generate relevant outputs for the PolicyCLOUD users (in the form of selected data visualizations);
- **User Data**, meaning the data which is collected from the actual individual users of the PDT, to allow the creation of user accounts and the general functioning of the PDT.

This information may be classifiable as “personal data”, to the extent that it can be traced back to natural person. Concerns which arise as a result of Policy Data are described in ‘D3.3 PolicyCLOUD Societal and Ethical Requirements and Guidelines’ [14], and should specifically be addressed by the different partners in charge of use cases, considering: (1) the data sources which the policy maker indicates as relevant for each use case scenario, including any legal/contractual constraints specific to their use, (2) the specific types of data to be collected from those data sources, and (3) the purposes for which the use case partners wish to have those data processed.

Where the PolicyCLOUD system is concerned, the main focus is on User Data, as the PME/PDT will serve as the entry point for such data and requires such data in order to function. Therefore, as outlined in D3.3 [14], the following ethical and legal concerns, as a minimum, will need to be addressed:

1. **Lawfulness.** An appropriate legal basis for each purpose for which personal data on PolicyCLOUD users may be collected should be identified, under Art. 6 GDPR. All steps needed to properly implement the identified legal bases should be taken – the specific steps will depend on the legal bases selected, which in turn depends on the ways in which User Data may be processed via the PolicyCLOUD.
2. **Fairness.** Personal data on PolicyCLOUD users should not be used in a manner which may violate their reasonable expectations. Profiling PolicyCLOUD users or covertly sharing their data with third parties for marketing purposes, for example, may qualify as unfair processing of personal data, in particular if this is not transparently disclosed to PolicyCLOUD users. There should also be mechanisms in place to ensure that PolicyCLOUD users are able to exercise their rights in relation to any personal data of theirs which may be collected during the use of the PolicyCLOUD (autonomously, or with assistance from PolicyCLOUD).
3. **Transparency.** A specific privacy policy should be developed for the PolicyCLOUD, to provide written information to users as to how their personal data may be handled when using the PolicyCLOUD in a concise, transparent, intelligible, and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language, meeting all the requirements of Arts. 13 and 14 GDPR. To the extent that cookies or similar tracking technologies are to be used on the PolicyCLOUD, this should be clearly

disclosed to users in this privacy policy, as well as in a separate cookie banner presented to PolicyCLOUD users upon accessing the PolicyCLOUD, offering users relevant choices as to their cookie preferences.

4. **Purpose limitation.** Personal data collected on PolicyCLOUD users should not be used for purposes which are incompatible with those declared in the privacy policy.
5. **Data minimization.** Only the strict minimum amount of personal data on PolicyCLOUD users needed to properly provide the PolicyCLOUD services, to perform any supporting functions, or for any other purpose for which a legal basis can be identified, should be collected and further processed.
6. **Accuracy.** PolicyCLOUD users should be given the possibility to rectify any personal data they submit, or which is collected on them, in connection with use of the PolicyCLOUD. This is linked to the above-described fairness principle.
7. **Storage limitation.** Personal data on PolicyCLOUD users may only be stored for the strict minimum amount of time needed to meet the purposes for which they were lawfully collected, after which such personal data should be irreversibly anonymized or deleted. This will require the identification of appropriate retention periods for personal data collected.
8. **Security.** Appropriate security measures to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of any collected and further stored personal data on PolicyCLOUD users, as well as the resilience of systems used to collect and further store those data, must be implemented.
9. **Accountability.** Records of evidence showing compliance with these requirements must be kept.

6.2 Constraints related to PolicyCLOUD Use

From the contractual perspective, it will be important to define terms and conditions for the acceptable use of the PolicyCLOUD, to properly regulate the service relationship established between PolicyCLOUD users, or the organization to which PolicyCLOUD users belong. These terms and conditions would need to be accepted for use of the PolicyCLOUD to be allowed and would form a binding contract upon PolicyCLOUD users / their organizations.

Matters which should be regulated within these terms and conditions include:

1. Description of the services offered through the PolicyCLOUD system;
2. Payment terms (if applicable);
3. Rules on acceptable use of the PolicyCLOUD;
4. Intellectual property (in particular, ownership of the PolicyCLOUD assets, the Policy Data and the PolicyCLOUD output);

5. Data protection (with reference to the privacy policy, as well as to a data management agreement or similar arrangement which may be put in place between the end-user and PolicyCLOUD);¹
6. Warranties and liability related to provision of the PolicyCLOUD system, in particular, considering the likelihood of statistical inaccuracies in output presented by the PolicyCLOUD and the use of such output to create public policies;
7. Warranties provided by the PolicyCLOUD user/their organization, and, in particular, compliance with legal and ethical requirements around selection of data sources and use of the PolicyCLOUD for policy making purposes;
8. Applicable law;
9. Modification of the terms and conditions;
10. Termination and effects of termination;
11. Other matters which may require contractual regulation, depending on the specific services to be provided.

6.3 Constraints related to Data Visualization

The data visualization component should, whenever feasible (considering the relevant Policy Data used and the purposes for which visualization is intended by the PolicyCLOUD user), not actually rely on, or disclose, information about identifiable individuals (i.e., “personal data”), but instead rely on appropriately anonymized/aggregated data, which cannot be traced back to any given specific and identified individual. This aims to ensure the protection of any such individuals and to avoid raising personal data protection concerns regarding the use of Policy Data or the output/visualizations produced by the PDT.

Where this is feasible, the core concerns around data visualization will be focused on:

1. **Statistical accuracy.** A failure to provide appropriate statistical results may ultimately lead to misleading or erroneous conclusions drawn by policymakers, culminating in misguided policy-making activities. As such, PolicyCLOUD should ensure that enough testing is performed to ensure a reasonable degree of statistical accuracy for these activities, and PolicyCLOUD users should be warned about the possibility of inaccuracies.

¹ When offering the PDT as a service, PolicyCLOUD may be acting, simultaneously, as a controller for some activities involving personal data and as a processor on behalf of the end-users. As such, entering a standard data processing agreement under Art. 28 GDPR may not suffice to fully regulate the data processing relationship between PolicyCLOUD and its end-users, as this would only cover the processor activities of PolicyCLOUD. To comprehensively regulate this relationship, the arrangement will need to include obligations to govern as well the PolicyCLOUD’s role as a controller. This can be done through a [data management agreement](#), which distinguishes between the different sets of processing activities performed and allocates different corresponding sets of obligations to each party, to ensure that it is clear to what extent each party will be responsible for complying with the different controller obligations laid out in the GDPR.

2. **Explainability of results.** For a PolicyCLOUD user to be able to use the PolicyCLOUD in a meaningful way, as a tool to support policy making while preserving their own accountability for the decisions taken regarding any specific policy, it is important that PolicyCLOUD users can understand the output presented to them by the PDT. Several different means can be conceived of to provide this information to PolicyCLOUD users. The most appropriate form of delivery, considering the user experience and context when operating the PolicyCLOUD, should be further assessed. Clear explanations should be given to PolicyCLOUD users on:
- Steps taken across the design and implementation of the PDT to ensure compliance with legal and ethical requirements, to maximize the security and robustness of the PDT, as well as the accuracy and reliability of the output;
 - The types of data sources and Policy Data used to produce outputs;
 - The rationale behind outputs, in terms of explaining generically how the Policy Data was processed to generate the outputs in question;
 - The likelihood of statistical inaccuracies in the outputs and the importance of critical examination and validation of output implications for policymaking by the PolicyCLOUD user.

The above requirements have been condensed (among other requirements applicable to components developed under WP5) into the **WP5 Legal/Ethical Checklist**, which serves to keep track of each requirement and progress made on its implementation, as the project develops.

7 Conclusion

This document is the second release of deliverable D5.2 [1] submitted in M8 (August 2020). It establishes the definition of the Public Policies (PPs) in the context of the PolicyCLOUD project and presents the methodologies based on ontologies and semantic reasoning that are being used for modelling of PPs. Moreover, it describes the specifications of the tools and technologies used to model PPs as well as the design of the Policy Development Toolkit (including the visualization framework), and the mechanisms required for compilation of policy collections to perform cross-sector analysis. Moreover, Finally, it details the legal ethical and privacy constraints and requirements related to WP5 activities.

This report will be further refined during the last phase of the project. There will be an additional version of this document in month M32 (August 2022) that will finalise the deliverable.

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